

Properties of Mixtures of Clay Minerals. Part II. Ternary Mixtures

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Studies have been made on the differential thermal analysis and on the variations in the pH, specific conductance, cationic activity, and viscosity on the progressive addition of bases to six ternary mixtures of kaolinite, montmorillonite, and illite. An examination of the total acidities and pH at inflection in the pH-base concentration curves, total acidity at the breaks of the conductometric titration curves, cationic dissociation, variation of viscosity on the addition of bases to H-clay mixtures, and the differential thermal analysis data indicates that individual constituents markedly influence the properties of other constituents in the mixture and the conclusion drawn from any single measurement is likely to lead to erroneous results. Attempts have been made to establish certain criteria for identification and estimation of individual clay mineral constituents in the mixtures.

As reported in Part I (this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 725), identification of individual components present in binary mixtures of clay minerals requires careful consideration of several aspects of the (i) potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of the H-systems with bases, (ii) D.T.A. curves, and (iii) variations in the viscosity of the H-systems with the progressive addition of bases. It has also been observed that conclusions drawn on the basis of any single measurement may often lead to erroneous results. The soils usually contain mixtures of three common clay minerals, viz., kaolinite, montmorillonite, and illite. With a view to establishing criteria which might be used for the identification and estimation of individual clay minerals commonly present in soils, ternary mixtures of varying composition of kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite have been subjected to differential thermal analysis and conductometric, potentiometric, and viscometric measurements. The different ternary mixtures used in the present study have the following compositions (proportions by weight on oven-dry basis):

TABLE A

	Kaolinite.		Illite.		Montmorillonite.
(a)	40%	+	20%	+	40%
(b)	80	+	10	+	10
(c)	10	+	30	+	60
(d)	40	+	40	+	20
(e)	10	+	10	+	80
(f)	10	+	80	+	10

The details of experimental procedures adopted were reported in Part I (Sarkar and Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*).

DISCUSSION

The D. T. A. diagrams of ternary mixtures, shown in Fig. 1, indicate that the endothermic peak near the region of 700° due to the presence of montmorillonite in the mixtures observed in all the mixtures with the exception of the ternary mixtures containing 10% montmorillonite. The individual endothermic peaks of kaolinite and illite in the zone of 500-600° could not be observed, but instead a single common endothermic peak was noticed. In this connection it will not be out of place to mention that according to Grim (*Am. Min.*, 1947, 32, 493), the thermal reactions of individual component of the mixtures are not always discernible, particularly if the mixing is very intimate and if the components are

poorly crystallised. The single exothermic peak for the ternary mixtures observed between 940° and 970° seems to indicate that kaolinite in the mixture exerts a greater influence on the position of the exothermic peak temperature and also on the size and sharpness of the resulting graph. This observation is true even when 10% kaolinite is present in the ternary mixture. The endothermic peak between 100° and 200° due to illite and montmorillonite is observed even in the mixture containing 10% illite, 10% montmorillonite, and 80% kaolinite.

FIG. 1. D.T.A. of ternary mixture of clay minerals.
K, I, and M denote respectively kaolinite, illite and montmorillonite.

Potentiometric and Conductometric Titration Curves

The potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of ternary mixtures have been shown in Figs. 2-7 and the results have been presented in Table I. The potentiometric titration curves of ternary mixtures of kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite show two inflex:

tion points—one in the region of pH 6.5–8.2 and the other between pH 10.1 and 10.8. Another inflection point at pH 8.4 has been observed only in the case of titration with KOH of a mixture containing 80% kaolinite, 10% illite, and 10% montmorillonite. The high total

FIG. 2. A mixture of 80% K+10% I+10% M.

FIG. 3. A mixture of 40% K+20% I+40% M.

acidity observed at the second inflection point between pH 10.1 and 10.8 may probably be attributed to the considerable buffer action of H-montmorillonite in this pH region. Thus, the third inflection point around pH 10.4 observed (Mitra and Rajagopalan, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 104) in the potentiometric titration curve of H-illite with bases is found only when an extra amount of base is added to overcome the buffer action due to the presence

of montmorillonite. It has been observed (Table II) that with one or two exceptions, the total acidity values observed at the first inflection point of the ternary mixtures are in general agreement with the calculated ones, based on the total acidities of kaolinite and illite at the second inflection point and that of montmorillonite at the first inflection point. The total acidity value observed at the second inflection point of the ternary mixture is found to be much greater than that calculated based on the total acidity of kaolinite at the second inflection point, that of illite at the third inflection point, and of

TABLE I

Total acidity of ternary mixture of clay minerals.

Samples.	Base used.	Total acid (m.e. per 100 g. of clay).				
		Potentiometric curves.			Conductometric curves.	
		1st inflec.	2nd inflec.	3rd inflec.	1st break.	2nd break.
1. H-kaolinite 80% + H-illite 10% + H-montmorillonite 10%	KOH	10.0(6.5)*	18.0(8.4)	36.5(10.3)	17.0	38.0
	Ca(OH) ₂	18.0(7.7)	50.0(10.2)	-	20.0	47.5
2. H-kaolinite 40% + H-illite 20% + H-montmorillonite 40%	KOH	38.0(7.6)	84.0(10.8)	-	44.0	80.0
	Ca(OH) ₂	45.0(7.1)	97.0(10.3)	-	51.0	100.0
3. H-kaolinite 40% + H-illite 40% + H-montmorillonite 20%	KOH	27.5(8.2)	49.0(10.2)	-	28.0	42.5
	Ca(OH) ₂	35.0(7.9)	62.0(10.1)	-	36.0	64.0
4. H-kaolinite 10% + H-illite 30% + H-montmorillonite 60%	KOH	57.0(7.7)	102.0(10.4)	-	58.0	100.0
	Ca(OH) ₂	65.0(7.2)	128.0(10.2)	-	70.0	112.0
5. H-kaolinite 10% + H-illite 10% + H-montmorillonite 80%	KOH	57.0(7.5)	130.0(10.6)	-		
6. H-kaolinite 10% + H-illite 80% + H-montmorillonite 10%	KOH	22.0(7.5)	58.0(10.5)	-		

*Figures within parenthesis denote pH at inflection.

TABLE II

Observed and calculated total acidities of ternary mixtures of clay minerals.

System.	Base used.	Total acidity at 1st inflec.		Total acidity at pH 7.0.		Total acidity at 2nd inflec.	
		(m.e. per 100g.)		(m.e./100g.)		(m.e./100g.)	
		Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
1. H-kaolinite 80% + H-illite 10% + H-montmorillonite 10%	KOH	10.0	20.0	12.0	15.9	18.0	23.2
	Ca(OH) ₂	18.0	21.0	16.5	14.5	50.0	25.8
2. H-kaolinite 40% + H-illite 20% + H-montmorillonite 40%	KOH	38.0	41.6	35.0	34.2	84.0	48.1
	Ca(OH) ₂	45.0	46.0	45.0	39.2	97.0	54.5
3. H-kaolinite 40% + H-illite 40% + H-montmorillonite 20%	KOH	27.5	33.8	21.5	25.6	49.0	46.7
	Ca(OH) ₂	35.0	38.4	30.0	27.8	62.0	55.3
4. H-kaolinite 10% + H-illite 30% + H-montmorillonite 60%	KOH	57.0	55.9	50.0	46.8	102.0	66.5
	Ca(OH) ₂	65.0	63.5	64.0	56.3	128.0	76.1
5. H-kaolinite 10% + H-illite 10% + H-montmorillonite 80%	KOH	57.0	64.7	54.0	55.8	130.0	67.9
6. H-kaolinite 10% + H-illite 80% + H-montmorillonite 10%	KOH	22.0	37.0	20.0	24.3	58.0	63.0

montmorillonite at the first inflection point. This discrepancy seems to arise on account of the great buffering action of H-montmorillonite in this pH region. The results obtained indicate that the five inflection points, viz., two for kaolinite, first two for illite, and one for montmorillonite, have probably merged into one and that the third inflection point, characteristic of illite, corresponds owing to the buffering action of H-montmorillonite to a higher total acidity (Mukherjee and Mitra, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1946, 1, 141; Mitra and Rajagopalan, *loc. cit.*; Sarkar and Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*).

Conductometric titration curves of ternary mixtures show two breaks corresponding to the inflections in the potentiometric titration curves. In case of the mixture containing 80% kaolinite, 10% illite, and 10% montmorillonite, the conductometric titration curve with KOH shows only two breaks, whereas the corresponding potentiometric titration curve shows three inflection points. The total acidities corresponding to the first and the second breaks of the former are more or less the same as those obtained from the second and third inflection points of the latter.

M. e. of base/100 g. of H-clay.
FIG. 4. A mixture of 40% K+40% I+20%M.

Viscometric Titrations of Ternary Mixtures of Clay Minerals

In the ternary mixtures (a), (c), (d), and (f) (Table A), the viscosity-KOH neutralisation curves (Figs. 3-5,7) show that viscosity initially remains unaffected with gradual addition of KOH up to about 20% neutralisation, then it rises to a maximum at about 70% neutralisation, and finally falls. The initial feature of the curve seems to be due to kaolinite (Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*) in the ternary mixtures and this is noticed even when 10% kaolinite is present (Figs. 5 and 7) except in the mixture (e) (Table A) which contains a large percentage of montmorillonite. In this case a gradual increase in viscosity is observed on the addition of KOH, which rises to a maximum at about 70% neutralisation (Fig. 6). The maximum viscosity observed in the viscosity-KOH curve of illite around 30-40% neutralisation is absent with all the ternary mixtures studied. The curve of the mixture (b) (Fig. 2) shows only the characteristics of kaolinite, i.e., a gradual fall in viscosity attaining finally a constant value. The viscosity data thus indicate that the presence of kaolinite or montmorillonite in large amounts (80% or so) masks the presence of the other

two in a ternary mixture, but in other cases, the viscosity—base concentration curves give an idea of the different clay minerals present in the mixture; the initial portions of the viscosity—base concentration curves of H-clays give an indication of the presence or otherwise of kaolinite in the mixture.

M. e. of base/100 g. of H-clay.
 FIG. 5. A mixture of 10% K+30% I+60%M.

M. e. of KOH/100 g. of H-clay.
 FIG. 6. 10% K+10% I+80%M.

M. e. of KOH/100 g. of H-clay.
 FIG. 7. 10% K+80% I+10%M.

Measurement of Cationic Activity

K⁺ ion and Ca²⁺ ion activity—base saturation curves of ternary mixtures, symbolised as a_{K^+} and $a_{Ca^{2+}}$ curves, are shown in Figs. 2-5 and the corresponding data in Table III,

TABLE III

Cationic fractions active in relation to clay minerals in mixtures.

Samples.		Assumed (m.e./100 g.).	Cation.	Fraction active.			Saturation.	
				25%.	50%.	75%.	100%.	125%.
Kaolinite	80%	18	K ⁺	0.40	0.220	0.200	0.190	0.180
Illite	10							
Montmorillonite	10	18	Ca ²⁺	0.09	0.044	0.032	0.033	0.030
Kaolinite	40	38	K ⁺	0.21	0.110	0.100	0.110	0.140
Illite	20							
Montmorillonite	40	45	Ca ²⁺	0.07	0.017	0.008	0.013	0.014
Kaolinite	40	27	K ⁺	0.22	0.110	0.100	0.110	0.150
Illite	40							
Montmorillonite	20	35	Ca ²⁺	0.06	0.020	0.011	0.017	0.018
Kaolinite	10	57	K ⁺	0.11	0.070	0.060	0.080	0.110
Illite	30							
Montmorillonite	60	65	Ca ²⁺	0.02	0.006	0.004	0.006	0.007

A comparison of a_{K^+} and $a_{Ca^{2+}}$ of the ternary mixtures indicates that the dissociation of these ions from these mixtures depends on the relative proportions of the individual clay mineral present. Thus, it has been observed that the mixture, which contains a larger amount of kaolinite, shows a higher cationic dissociation compared to the one which contains more of montmorillonite (Chatterjee and Marshall, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 671).

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